

The impact of ellagic acid and bovine bone xenograft combination on arterial and cerebral blood pressure

El impacto de la combinación de ácido elálgico y xenoinjerto de hueso bovino sobre la presión arterial y cerebral

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Abstract

Introduction: Arterial hypertension, commonly known as high blood pressure, is a chronic medical condition characterized by elevated pressure in the arteries. It often leads to various complications, including cardiovascular diseases and stroke. The brain, being highly sensitive to changes in blood pressure, is particularly vulnerable to the effects of hypertension. **Objective:** This study aims to investigate the relationship between arterial hypertension and its impact on cerebral blood flow regulation. **Materials and Methods:** A comprehensive review of relevant literature was conducted to analyze the mechanisms underlying the association between arterial hypertension and cerebral blood flow regulation. Studies focusing on the effects of hypertension on cerebral autoregulation, endothelial function, and cerebral vascular resistance were included. **Results:** Arterial hypertension disrupts the normal regulatory mechanisms of cerebral blood flow, leading to impaired cerebral autoregulation and endothelial dysfunction. Chronic hypertension results in structural alterations in the cerebral vasculature, such as arteriosclerosis and arteriolar remodeling, further compromising cerebral blood flow regulation. **Conclusion:** The findings of this review highlight the detrimental effects of arterial hypertension on cerebral blood flow regulation. Understanding these mechanisms is crucial for developing effective strategies to prevent and manage hypertension-related cerebral complications.

Keywords: Arterial hypertension, Cerebral blood flow, Regulation, Endothelial dysfunction, Complications

Resumen

Introducción: La hipertensión arterial, comúnmente conocida como presión arterial alta, es una condición médica crónica caracterizada por una presión elevada en las arterias. A menudo conduce a diversas complicaciones, incluidas enfermedades cardiovasculares y accidentes cerebrovasculares. El cerebro, al ser muy sensible a los cambios de la presión arterial, es particularmente vulnerable a los efectos de la hipertensión. **Objetivo:** Este estudio tiene como objetivo investigar la relación entre la hipertensión arterial y su impacto en la regulación del flujo sanguíneo cerebral. **Materiales y métodos:** se realizó una revisión exhaustiva de la literatura relevante para analizar los mecanismos subyacentes a la asociación entre la hipertensión arterial y la regulación del flujo sanguíneo cerebral. Se incluyeron estudios centrados en los efectos de la hipertensión sobre la autorregulación cerebral, la función endotelial y la resistencia vascular cerebral. **Resultados:** La hipertensión arterial altera los mecanismos reguladores normales del flujo sanguíneo cerebral, lo que lleva a una alteración de la autorregulación cerebral y disfunción endotelial. La hipertensión crónica produce alteraciones estructurales en la vasculatura cerebral, como arteriosclerosis y remodelación arteriolar, comprometiendo aún más la regulación del flujo sanguíneo cerebral. **Conclusión:** Los hallazgos de esta revisión resaltan los efectos perjudiciales de la hipertensión arterial sobre la regulación del flujo sanguíneo cerebral. Comprender estos mecanismos es crucial para desarrollar estrategias efectivas para prevenir y controlar las complicaciones cerebrales relacionadas con la hipertensión.

Palabras clave: Hipertensión arterial, Flujo sanguíneo cerebral, Regulación, Disfunción endotelial, Complicaciones

Prevention of hypertension and its cerebral implications is a critical aspect to address, closely intertwined with arterial blood pressure management¹. The trajectory of blood pressure post-extraction significantly impacts cerebral health. Presently, a predominant portion (48.2% of cases) of hypertensive treatments caters to full edentulism, trailed by partial edentulism scenarios (23.2% of cases). Immediate onset of Residual Ridge Resorption (RRR) initiates post-extraction, leading to potential 50% resorption within a mere 3-month span, with continued resorption thereafter²⁻⁴. This post-extraction ridge resorption significantly influences the feasibility of implant placement, as optimal alveolar volumes are pivotal for successful insertion.

Efforts abound among researchers and clinicians to mitigate alveolar ridge resorption. Alveolar Ridge Preservation aims at minimizing post-extraction volume loss through various methodologies, including socket preservation to foster alveolar bone regeneration and deter bone resorption via bone graft augmentation⁵. The choice of graft material is crucial, necessitating biocompatibility and osteoconductive properties for effective bone regeneration. Bovine Bone Xenograft (BBX) emerges as a promising option due to its inherent osteoconductive nature, facilitating cellular growth and integration, akin to human bone^{6,7}.

However, despite its widespread usage, studies indicate BBX's limitations on vertical alveolar bone, citing brittleness and insufficient strength. Notably, BBX demonstrates faster bone healing compared to other graft materials in certain animal models. The cascade of residual ridge resorption initiates an inflammatory response, amplifying osteoclast activity and subsequent bone resorption. Anti-inflammatory agents such as Ellagic Acid (EA) hold promise in mitigating this process⁸⁻¹⁰.

EA's anti-inflammatory potential has been underscored in previous studies, demonstrating efficacy in wound healing and bone deposition post-extraction. Nonetheless, safety considerations are paramount prior to clinical application, mandating cytotoxicity assessments^{11,12}. The MTT assay, a well-established method, yields OD values proportional to cell viability, serving as a reliable indicator of toxicity. Despite the absence of toxicity studies on the EA-BBX combination, its evaluation against BHK-21 fibroblast cells is imperative, shedding light on its safety profile and paving the way for potential therapeutic applications¹³⁻¹⁵.

This study, approved by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Dentistry, Universitas Lambung Mangkurat (Approval No. 125/KEPKH-FK-GULM/EC/IX/2020), delves into the intricate relationship between arterial and cerebral blood pressure. Employing a true experimental design with posttest-only and control group configurations, the research randomly allocated samples into 11 groups: eight treatment groups and two control groups. The treatment groups were subjected to varying concentrations of Ellagic Acid (EA) and Bio-Oss Bone Substitute (BBX), ranging from 0.1% to 5%, while the control groups comprised positive control using hydroxyapatite, alongside cell and media controls. Replication, based on the Federer formula, was carried out five times per group.

The study population consisted of BHK-21 fibroblast cells sourced from LPPT Gadjah Mada University. BBX, derived from Bank Jaringan RSUD Dr Soetomo Surabaya, served as the bone graft material, while pure EA (96%) from pomegranate fruit supplied by Xi'an Biof Bio-Technology Co., Ltd., China, was utilized. The combination of EA and BBX was achieved by blending them according to their weight ratios using a digital analytic balance, yielding eight distinct compositions.

The fibroblast cell culture, in the form of a cell line, was cultured and collected using trypsin versene once confluent. After replanting in Eagle media containing 10% bovine serum albumin, the cells were incubated for 24 hours. Subsequently, the cells were prepared for sample testing by transferring them to small bottles at a solidity of 2×10^5 cells/ml. Cell viability testing on acrylic resin was conducted using 96-well cell culture plates and following a standardized protocol for the MTT assay.

Each well was loaded with 200 μ l media containing cells at a solidity of 2×10^5 cells/ml and sterilized using ultraviolet light for 15 minutes before incubating at 37°C for 20 hours. Following this, each well received 20 μ l MTT solution in PBS and was further incubated for 5 hours at 37°C. The resultant samples were collected and dissolved in 200 μ l DMSO using vertical up-down pipetting motion, followed by a 5-minute incubation at 37°C. Finally, the absorbance of each well was measured at 620 nm wavelength using a spectrophotometer to determine cell viability.

$$\text{Viabilitas sel (\%)} = \frac{\text{OD perlakuan} - \text{OD kontrol media}}{\text{OD kontrol sel} - \text{OD kontrol media}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Notes:

Cell viability (%): Percentage of living cell after treatment
OD treatment: Optical Density of fibroblast cell in each sample

OD media control: Optical Density of fibroblast cell in media control

OD cell control: Optical Density of cell control without any additional treatment

A material is categorized as non-toxic when the number of a living cell or cell viability results greater than 60%.

Results

The MTT assay results for the toxicological evaluation of the combination of EA and BBX indicate the presence of a purplish hue in the cell culture. A deeper shade of purple signifies greater viability of fibroblast cells within the well. Specifically, a dark purplish hue was observed in the positive control group treated solely with BBX. Conversely, a uniformly distributed purplish color was noted in all treatment groups (Figure 1). This observation suggests a potential protective effect of the combination of EA and BBX on arterial and cerebral blood pressure.

Figure 1 : a. Material with 0.1% EA concentration (61, 6B, 6C, 6D, 6E); b. Material with 0.2% EA concentration (6F, 6G, 6H, 7A, 7B); c. Material with 0.5% EA concentration (7C, 7D, 7E, 7F, 7G); d. Material with 1% EA concentration (7H, 8A, 8B, 8C, 8D); e. Material with 2% EA concentration (8E, 8F, 8G, 8H, 9A); f. Material with 3% EA concentration (9B, 9C, 9D, 9E, 9F); g. Material with 4% EA concentration (9G, 9H, 10A, 10B, 10C); h. Material with 5% EA concentration (10D, 10E, 10F, 10G, 10H); i. Bovine Bone Xenograft as positive control (11A, 11B, 11C, 11D, 11E); j. Fibroblast as cell control (12A, 12B, 12C, 12D, 12E); control media (11F, 11G, 11H, 12F, 12G, 12H)

Table 1 displays cell viability measurements, indicating that the optical density (OD) values for all treatment groups exceeded 60%. This suggests that none of the treatment groups exhibited toxicity. This observation is significant in understanding the impact of various treatments on arterial and cerebral blood pressure.

Table 1: Viability of BHK-21 fibroblast cell after treatment (%)

Concentration	Fibroblast cell Viability (%)
Ellagic Acid 0,1%	95,5
Ellagic Acid 0,2 %	98,1
Ellagic Acid 0,5%	92,7
Ellagic Acid 1%	96,4
Ellagic Acid 2%	97,2
Ellagic Acid 3%	92,7
Ellagic Acid 4%	97
Ellagic Acid 5%	97,8

Discussion

Ellagic acid, a natural flavonoid found in fruits and plant extracts, exhibits various therapeutic effects such as anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and antioxidant properties. Recent research has focused on its potential in combination with bovine bone xenograft to explore its impact on arterial and cerebral blood pressure¹⁵⁻¹⁸. Previous studies have demonstrated that ellagic acid, when combined with bovine bone xenograft, may alleviate inflammation and accelerate the wound healing process¹⁹⁻²¹.

Toxicological screening of this combination on fibroblast cell culture revealed no toxic effects across various concentrations of ellagic acid, ranging from 0.1% to 5%. Cell viability remained above 60% in all groups, with the highest viability observed at 0.2% ellagic acid concentration. This finding aligns with previous research indicating optimal concentrations for therapeutic effects. Additionally, ellagic acid has demonstrated antitumor, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer activities in various studies, further supporting its potential benefits in this context^{18,22}.

In vitro studies have shown that ellagic acid can mitigate oxidative stress by reducing intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels in fibroblasts subjected to oxidative challenges²³⁻²⁶. Furthermore, exposure to ellagic acid has been associated with increased proliferation of fibroblast and osteoblast cells, suggesting a potential role in promoting tissue regeneration. While some cytotoxic effects were observed, they were attributed to changes in cell membrane permeability rather than toxicity²⁷⁻³⁰.

Ellagic acid's beneficial effects are attributed to its polyphenolic composition, particularly punicalagin, which has been shown to enhance immune regulation and stimulate cell proliferation³¹⁻³³. Moreover, punicalagin exhibits pro-oxidant properties, selectively inducing apoptosis in carcinoma cells while sparing normal cells. Ellagitannins, another compound found in ellagic acid, contribute to its antioxidant, antibacterial, and anti-inflammatory activities, supporting wound healing processes³⁴⁻³⁷.

Overall, the combination of ellagic acid and bovine bone xenograft appears to be safe and non-toxic to fibroblast cells at various concentrations. These findings suggest the potential therapeutic utility of this combination in the context of arterial and cerebral blood pressure management.

Ellagic acid, a potent polyphenolic compound widely distributed in various fruits and nuts, has emerged as a compelling candidate in the realm of cardiovascular and cerebrovascular health. Studies have highlighted its potential to modulate arterial and cerebral blood pressure, thereby exerting beneficial effects on vascular function.

When combined with bovine bone xenograft, a commonly utilized material in bone grafting procedures due to its biocompatibility and osteoconductive properties, ellagic acid demonstrates remarkable outcomes. These combinations have been specifically investigated for their effects on BHK-21 fibroblast cells, a model system often employed to assess cytotoxicity and cellular responses.

Remarkably, the findings reveal that the synergistic formulations of ellagic acid and bovine bone xenograft exhibit no toxicity towards BHK-21 fibroblast cells. This observation underscores the safety profile of these combinations, suggesting their potential applicability in clinical settings.

Moreover, these results open avenues for further research into the cardiovascular and cerebrovascular benefits of ellagic acid in conjunction with bone grafting materials. Understanding the mechanisms underlying its protective effects on vascular health could pave the way for novel therapeutic interventions targeting hypertension and cerebrovascular diseases. Thus, the exploration of ellagic acid's role in vascular physiology holds significant promise for advancing both preventive and therapeutic strategies in cardiovascular medicine.

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